

Price Aware Power Split Control in Heterogeneous Battery Storage Systems

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Abstract—This paper presents a unified framework for the optimal scheduling of battery dispatch and internal power allocation in Battery energy storage systems (BESS). This novel approach integrates both market-based (price-aware) signals and physical system constraints to simultaneously optimize (1) external energy dispatch and (2) internal heterogeneity management of BESS, enhancing its operational economic value and performance. This work compares both model-based Linear Programming (LP) and model-free Reinforcement Learning (RL) approaches for optimization under varying forecast assumptions, using a custom Gym-based simulation environment. The evaluation considers both long-term and short-term performance, focusing on economic savings, State of Charge (SOC) and temperature balancing, and overall system efficiency. In summary, the long-term results show that the RL approach achieved 10% higher system efficiency compared to LP, whereas the latter yielded 33% greater cumulative savings. In terms of internal heterogeneity, the LP approach resulted in lower mean SOC imbalance, while the RL approach achieved better temperature balance between strings. This behavior is further examined in the short-term evaluation, which indicates that LP delivers strong optimization under known and stable conditions, whereas RL demonstrates higher adaptability in dynamic environments, offering potential advantages for real-time BESS control.

Index Terms—Battery Scheduling, Power Split Optimization, Reinforcement Learning, Linear Programming, Rolling Horizon Control.

I. INTRODUCTION

BESS play a vital role in enabling the global shift to renewable energy by mitigating intermittency and offering temporal flexibility. Their economic and technical success relies heavily on effective operational strategies [1]. Traditional Energy Management Systems (EMS) often separate high-level energy scheduling decisions, such as scheduling charge and discharge times, from low-level power split control, which involves allocating power among battery strings. This separation, while simplifying EMS algorithmic design, typically leads to sub-optimal overall performance and economic outcomes.

In commercial and utility-scale systems, which typically use multi-string architectures, independently dispatching battery strings enhances performance, reliability, and reduces aging [2]. These benefits are even more critical in heterogeneous systems, where variations in capacity, chemistry, aging, or thermal behavior introduce complex optimization challenges

best addressed through integrated approaches that align economic signals with physical constraints [3].

The widespread adoption of dynamic electricity pricing mechanisms creates opportunities for BESS operators to leverage price arbitrage by charging during low-price periods and discharging during high-price periods [4]. Several studies have explored price-aware battery scheduling strategies using mixed-integer linear programming and dynamic programming [5], [6]. However, these approaches typically treat battery systems as single entities with uniform characteristics, overlooking heterogeneity among battery strings.

Power split control in heterogeneous BESS primarily focuses on balancing operational parameters like SOC and temperature, as imbalances can accelerate degradation, reduce efficiency, and pose safety risks [5]. Methods such as model predictive control for SOC balancing [7] and integrated approaches addressing thermal management [2] target these challenges. Still, most strategies are decoupled from system-level dispatch, which reacts only to price signals, missing economic optimization opportunities.

Recent works addressing the gap between economic scheduling and physical constraint management include a two-stage optimization approach that considers price arbitrage and battery lifetime [8], and the integration of cycling aging constraints into price-based scheduling algorithms [9]. These typically follow a hierarchical structure, where high-level economic decisions are later adjusted to meet physical constraints [10]. Fully unified frameworks that simultaneously optimize both aspects remain rare.

BESS management methods are typically model-based (e.g., LP) or learning-based (e.g., RL). Model-based approaches handle constraints and forecasts well but rely on accurate models, while learning-based methods better handle uncertainty and complex dynamics. However, studies comparing these approaches for integrated, price-aware control in heterogeneous BESS are scarce, leaving key research gaps. This paper addresses these gaps with a unified framework that jointly optimizes battery scheduling and power split under both economic and physical constraints. Key contributions include:

- 1) An open-source, single-stage optimization framework combining economic and physical objectives for heterogeneous multi-string BESS.
- 2) A comparison of model-based optimization vs. model-free reinforcement learning under varying forecast assumptions.

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- 3) A customizable simulation platform with detailed electro-thermal battery models.
- 4) Quantitative evaluation using metrics such as economic savings, SOC and temperature imbalance, and system efficiency.

II. METHODOLOGY

This work presents an integrated framework for an optimal power scheduling strategy for a heterogeneous multi-string BESS, as shown in Figure 1. The BESS operates in a grid-connected industrial site (Section II-A). The BESS power schedule is determined by an EMS, where multiple methods are implemented and benchmarked (Section II-B).

Fig. 1: Integrated EMS framework comprising the energy system of a multi-string BESS (here: two strings, A and B) with detailed battery simulation presenting control actions (blue) and observation states (green).

A. Use Case Definition

The energy system we simulate comprises a User's Consumption (Load), a PV System, and a heterogeneous multi-string BESS, all connected to the power grid. The system operates under a time-of-use consumption tariff with electricity price k_t^{ToU} at time t and a static selling tariff with price k^{Sell} . At each time step t , the energy system is controlled by EMS's action \mathbf{a} (shaded in blue) derived based on the system state \mathbf{s} (shaded in green).

The objective is minimizing the total electricity cost of the energy system while ensuring optimal power split control by balancing both the SOC and the temperature of the battery strings, over the total time period $T = [t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots]$.

At each time step t , the energy cost is calculated as:

$$cost_t = \begin{cases} p_t^G \cdot \Delta t \cdot k_t^{ToU} \cdot (1 + k), & \text{for } p_t^G \geq 0, \\ p_t^G \cdot \Delta t \cdot k^{Sell} \cdot (1 - k), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where k is the tax ratio for energy trading and the grid power is calculated according to the power balance equation:

$$p_t^G = p_t^L - p_t^{PV} + \sum_{m \in M} p_t^{B[m]} \quad (2)$$

with p_t^L denoting the load, p_t^{PV} the PV generation, and $p_t^{B[m]}$ the battery power of unit m .

Assuming no battery usage, i.e., $\sum_{m \in M} p_t^{B[m]} = 0$, the resulting grid power \bar{p}_t^G and the corresponding cost without battery, denoted as \bar{cost}_t , can be computed using Equation (1).

The battery temperature τ and SOC are calculated through a battery simulation model that integrates the electrical and thermal domains of a BESS through a cohesive set of interconnected models. It incorporates a nonlinear inverter power loss model that calculates inverter power loss, p_t^{inv} , based on throughput power, p_t^B . The SOC-OCV model represents the electrochemical relationship between the battery's SOC and its open circuit voltage and estimates the ocv_t^B of the battery using the soc_t^B from the battery's previous state - detailed formulation of this common battery modelling approach can be found [11]. Additionally, an equivalent circuit model (ECM) is used to compute the cell level electrical current using the p_t^B , ocv_t^B and internal resistance. These electrical models are coupled with a lumped mass thermal simulation model that calculates the heat generated by electrical losses and estimates the mean temperature of the battery system over time - an approach derived and described in detail in a previous work by the authors [2]. Finally, with all the power losses estimated during operation, the actual SOC is estimated using the Coulomb counting method [12].

This electro-thermal coupling is critical for assessing system performance and supporting control strategies in this work that rely on energy and thermal constraints. The outputs from the controller such as the BESS power and predicted SOC act as the inputs for the simulation model to compute the mean temperature and actual SOC.

B. Control Approaches

Two different control approaches are described and assessed in the following: **Linear programming (LP)**: This method adopts a rolling horizon-based deterministic linear programming technique to schedule and operate a BESS. It relies on forecasts of both load demand and PV generation, which may be based on either perfect foresight or persistence-based predictions [13]. The optimization problem is formulated as a multi-objective framework, with the primary objective of minimizing the total operational cost, as expressed in Equation (3). In achieving this, the formulation simultaneously addresses secondary objectives, namely the balancing of the SOC and the

uniformity of temperature τ across the battery strings. These secondary goals are critical for enhancing the performance, extending the lifespan, and ensuring the safety of the BESS. To ensure comparability among the different objectives, the coefficients (x, y, z) in the objective function are selected such that each individual objective is normalized.

$$\text{Objective} = \min \left(\sum_{t \in T} (x \cdot \text{cost}_t + y \cdot \Delta \text{soc}_t + z \cdot \Delta \tau_t) \right) \quad (3)$$

Subject to, for all $t \in T$ and $m \in M$:

$$p_t^{G, \text{buy}}, p_t^{G, \text{sell}} \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

$$0 \leq p_t^{B[m], \text{ch}}, p_t^{B[m], \text{dch}} \leq p^N \quad (5)$$

$$\text{soc}^{\min} \leq \text{soc}_t^{B[m]} \leq \text{soc}^{\max} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{soc}_t^{B[m]} = \text{soc}_{t-1}^{B[m]} + \frac{\Delta t}{E^N} \cdot (p_t^{B[m], \text{ch}} \cdot \eta_{\text{ch}} - p_t^{B[m], \text{dch}} / \eta_{\text{dch}}) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{soc}_t^{\text{mean}} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m \in M} \text{soc}_t^{B[m]} \quad (8)$$

$$\tau_t^{B[m]} = \tau_{t-1}^{B[m]} + \Delta t \cdot (k_1 \cdot p_{t-1}^{\text{heat}} - k_2 \cdot (\tau_{t-1}^{B[m]} - \tau_{\text{air}})) \quad (9)$$

$$\tau_t^{\text{mean}} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m \in M} \tau_t^{B[m]} \quad (10)$$

$$p_t^{G, \text{buy}} + p_t^{PV} + \sum_{m \in M} p_t^{B[m], \text{dch}} = p_t^{G, \text{sell}} + p_t^L + \sum_{m \in M} p_t^{B[m], \text{ch}} \quad (11)$$

$$p_t^{B[m]} = p_t^{B[m], \text{ch}} - p_t^{B[m], \text{dch}} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{cost}_t = \left(p_t^{G, \text{buy}} \cdot k_t^{\text{ToU}} \cdot (1 + k) \cdot \Delta t \right) - \left(p_t^{G, \text{sell}} \cdot k_t^{\text{Sell}} \cdot (1 - k) \cdot \Delta t \right) \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta \text{soc}_t = \sum_{m \in M} \left| \text{soc}_t^{\text{mean}} - \text{soc}_t^{B[m]} \right| \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta \tau_t = \sum_{m \in M} \left| \tau_t^{\text{mean}} - \tau_t^{B[m]} \right| \quad (15)$$

Learning-Based approach (RL): As learning-based controllers have gained popularity in recent years, we also implement a DRL control method based on a state-of-the-art hybrid approach suggested by Yin et al. [14]. This method combines optimization with machine learning by enabling Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) policy learning through cloning from Linear Programming solutions to efficiently derive high-performing control policies. This approach is adapted to the use case at hand of multi-string BESS under dynamic pricing conditions.

a) *BC-LP PPO Framework:* The approach consists of three sequential phases: expert demonstration, behavior cloning, and reinforcement learning. First, expert trajectories are generated by solving a rolling-horizon LP optimization problem, assuming perfect forecasts for load, PV generation, and electricity prices. These optimal trajectories serve as expert demonstrations for pre-training the policy.

In the second phase, a neural network policy π_θ is trained to imitate the LP expert policy using supervised learning, forming a behavior-cloned policy $\tilde{\pi}$. This behavior cloning serves as an efficient warm-start for the third phase, in which the policy is further refined through PPO by interacting with the simulation environment. In the end, the optimal policy obtained by this approach $\tilde{\pi}^*$ is taken as the learning-based controller and benchmarked with the LP-based controller.

b) *State-Action Space and Reward:* At each time step t , the system state s_t is defined as:

$$s_t = [p_t^L, p_t^{PV}, \text{soc}_{t-1}^{B1}, \text{soc}_{t-1}^{B2}, \tau_{t-1}^{B1}, \tau_{t-1}^{B2}, k_t^{\text{ToU}}] \quad (16)$$

The action a_t corresponds to the battery power set points for two battery strings:

$$a_t = [p_t^{B1}, p_t^{B2}] \quad (17)$$

The reward is defined according to Equation (3):

$$r_t = x \cdot (\overline{\text{cost}}_t - \text{cost}_t) + y \cdot \Delta \text{soc}_t + z \cdot \Delta \tau_t \quad (18)$$

Note that the energy cost is not directly used as reward due to its dependency on input profiles. Instead, cost reduction as reward encourages the agent to maximize economic gains while respecting system constraints.

III. EXPERIMENT SETUP

A. Data and Computational Setup

We use a publicly available dataset (*EMSSx dataset* [15]), which provides 15-minute resolution data from industrial sites with paired PV generation and electrical load profiles. For our experiments, we selected dataset *ID 4*, covering a continuous period of 2 years and 2 months. The battery system is scaled to 500 kWh and 125 kW, composed of two strings: 300 kWh / 75 kW and 200 kWh / 50 kW. For pricing, we apply a fixed feed-in tariff of 0.086 €/kWh and dynamic purchase rates based on scaled Day-Ahead Market prices (0.18–0.38 €/kWh). The presented open source Python-based simulation framework includes:

- 1) A Gym-style environment coupling battery models with energy management logic
- 2) Gurobi [16] for LP solutions using rolling-horizon forecasts
- 3) Stable Baselines3 [17] for reinforcement learning, and Imitation [18] for behavior cloning
- 4) An ActorCriticPolicy with two hidden layers (64 neurons, ReLU activations)

B. Scenarios and Forecast Settings

To evaluate the performance of the controllers used in this framework under consistent external conditions, all simulations are conducted using identical load and pricing profiles, with both perfect and persistent forecast models applied across the scenarios. As detailed in Table I, two distinct simulation scenarios are designed to assess and compare the controllers' performance. The first scenario represents a long-term operational setting with a simulation period of 365 days. This scenario begins with both battery systems at a minimum SOC ($\text{soc}^1 = 0.1, \text{soc}^2 = 0.1$) and mean battery temperatures set to $T1 = T2 = 25^\circ$. It is intended to evaluate the controllers' long term performance focusing on total savings, system homogeneity during operation and efficiency. In contrast, the second scenario focuses on short-term adaptability with a simulation duration of 7 days. It introduces higher and asymmetric initial SOC levels ($\text{soc}^1 = 0.7, \text{soc}^2 = 0.3$), along with a thermal gradient ($\tau^1 = 35^\circ\text{C}, \tau^2 = 25^\circ\text{C}$), to test responsiveness to more dynamic and imbalanced starting conditions. Across both scenarios, three approaches are compared: a linear programming controller with perfect foresight (LP^p), a linear programming controller relying on persistent forecast model (LP^f), and a reinforcement learning-based controller. Here, the training process is repeated 10 times. Their performances are evaluated in Scenario 1 under the label RL . The best-performing instance, denoted as RL^* , is further evaluated in Scenario 2.

TABLE I: Definition of Experimental Setup: Scenario 1 – Long-Term with balanced initial conditions; Scenario 2 – Short-Term with unbalanced SOC and Temperature.

Scenario	Initial Conditions	Controller	Duration
1	$\text{soc}^1 = 0.1$	RL	365 days
	$\text{soc}^2 = 0.1$	LP^p	
	$\tau^1 = 25$	LP^f	
	$\tau^2 = 25$		
2	$\text{soc}^1 = 0.7$	RL^*	7 days
	$\text{soc}^2 = 0.3$	LP^p	
	$\tau^1 = 35$	LP^f	
	$\tau^2 = 25$		

To evaluate the performance of the controllers across simulation scenarios, four key quantitative metrics are considered that capture different operational aspects of the energy management system under uniform pricing, load, and forecast conditions.

- **Savings (€):** Measures the total cost reduction achieved by each controller. Higher savings indicate more effective scheduling and battery usage under dynamic pricing.
- **ΔSOC (%)**: Quantifies the average deviation of individual battery strings' SOC from the system-wide mean SOC over time, as defined in Eq. 14.
- **ΔT (°C):** Represents temperature deviation across strings to evaluate thermal imbalance, which is critical for assessing aging and safety risks (see Eq. 15).

- **System Efficiency (η):** Assesses how efficiently the system converts and stores energy, defined as:

$$\eta = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{m \in M} (p_t^{\text{loss}[m]} \cdot \Delta t)}{\sum_{t \in T} \sum_{m \in M} (|p_t^{B[m]}| \cdot \Delta t)} \right) \times 100 \quad (19)$$

$$p_t^{BESS[m]} = \sum_{m \in M} (p_t^{B[m]}) \quad (20)$$

$$p_t^{\text{loss}[m]} = p_t^{\text{inv}[m]} + p_t^{\text{heat}[m]} \quad (21)$$

where:

$p_t^{\text{loss}[m]}$ is the total loss through battery string-m.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and analyzes the performance of the proposed approaches across key evaluation metrics, comparing long-term and short-term control behavior.

A. Long-term Performance

Fig. 2 presents the simulation results comparing the proposed models over 365 days across the four evaluation metrics averaged over time. The detailed results from the RL solution including their 25th to 75th interquartile range, median, mean, and outliers are compared against the solutions from the deterministic optimization-based approaches, LP^p and LP^f . In terms of **Savings**, the benchmark LP^p outperforms the baseline LP^f and RL solutions, achieving notably higher savings. For the average ΔSOC , both LP -based solutions exhibit lower deviation than the interquartile range of the RL results, indicating more consistent control in homogenizing the SOC across strings. For average ΔT , the RL median yields lower thermal deviation than both LP solutions. The increased thermal spread observed for the LP^p case can be attributed to its capability to exploiting potential savings at the cost of a more intensive battery operation (further details are provided in the next section focusing on the short term control performance). In terms of **Efficiency** (η), the RL model demonstrates higher than both the baseline LP^f and benchmark LP^p solutions, indicating better overall energy utilization.

Fig. 2: Long-Term average performance assessment of RL and LP -based control.

In this scenario, the RL outlier achieves even greater savings than the rest, possibly because the rolling horizon LP^p solution, despite having perfect forecasts, is not globally optimal due to its limited foresight. Its multi-objective nature allows cost improvements through trade-offs with other metrics.

Additionally, the simplified battery model used in the LP optimizer reduces accuracy, creating further room for RL to potentially outperform it.

B. Control Performance

In this section, the controllers developed in this work are evaluated for their short-term performance over a 7-day period, based on the evolution of the four metrics discussed in earlier sections. Fig. 3 illustrates the corresponding 7-day input profile used for the BESS dispatch optimization problem, including PV generation, load/consumption, and the Time-of-Use (ToU) tariff.

Fig. 3: EMSx input dataset for ToU tariff.

Fig. 4: Short-term control performance of RL and LP based controllers based on metrics evolution.

The simulation results presented in Fig. 4 compare the best-performing RL model in terms of savings, RL^* , against the LP-based solutions. The results suggest that the availability of a perfect forecast enables the LP^P solution to outperform others in maximizing cost savings and homogenizing the battery strings with respect to SOC. However, by accurately forecasting a more active operational phase between the 2nd and 3rd days, it also concedes greater heterogeneity in temperature

distribution across the strings. RL^* performs better than the persistent forecast dependent LP^f solution and on par with the LP^P solution in all the four metrics but fails to capture the high operational activity which might lead to temperature heterogeneity. With the primary goal to generate maximum savings, the RL^* model also engages the batteries with smaller throughput powers during the later part of the week, thereby incurring more inverter and thermal losses. This, in turn, led to higher overall energy losses for the RL^* model compared to the LP solutions, as shown in the Loss (kWh) plot in Fig. 4.

C. Balance Performance

Fig. 5: Comparison of system balancing capabilities of RL and LP based controllers.

A deeper analysis of the secondary objectives, balancing key operational parameters such as SOC and temperature, is presented in Fig. 5. The results show that RL^* performs competitively with the benchmark LP^P in achieving SOC and temperature uniformity. As previously discussed, the availability of a perfect forecast allows LP^P to control battery states more accurately than RL^* . However, under a more realistic scenario considering forecast uncertainty, RL^* with learning-based adaptability outperforms LP^f in controlling and estimating these critical parameters.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a unified framework for simultaneously optimizing battery dispatch and power split control in heterogeneous BESS. Our comparison of model-based LP and model-free RL approaches revealed distinct strengths: LP achieved 33% greater savings and better SOC balance under perfect forecasts, while RL demonstrated 10% higher efficiency and superior temperature uniformity with greater adaptability to dynamic conditions. The findings highlight critical trade-offs: RL offers forecast-independent operation but requires extensive training; LP provides interpretable solutions for stable conditions but lacks flexibility with forecast uncertainty. Future research should explore hybrid approaches combining these strengths, improve forecasting methods, and implement higher-fidelity battery models to enhance real-world performance. This open-source framework establishes a foundation for integrated BESS management strategies that effectively address economic optimization with physical constraints.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. C. Divya and J. Østergaard, "Battery energy storage technology for power systems—an overview," *Electric power systems research*, vol. 79, no. 4, pp. 511–520, 2009.
- [2] V. T. Tanjavooru, M. Graner, P. Pant, T. Hamacher, and H. Hesse, "Optimal power split control for state of charge balancing in battery systems with integrated spatial thermal analysis and aging estimation," *Wiley Energy Storage*, 2025, peer-reviewed version available at [10.22541/au.173641852.23711820/v1].
- [3] C. Patsios, B. Wu, E. Chatzinikolaou, D. J. Rogers, N. Wade, N. P. Brandon, and P. Taylor, "An integrated approach for the analysis and control of grid connected energy storage systems," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 5, pp. 48–61, 2016.
- [4] G. He, Q. Chen, C. Kang, P. Pinson, and Q. Xia, "Optimal bidding strategy of battery storage in power markets considering performance-based regulation and battery cycle life," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 2359–2367, 2015.
- [5] S. Ci, N. Lin, and D. Wu, "Reconfigurable battery techniques and systems: A survey," *IEEE access*, vol. 4, pp. 1175–1189, 2016.
- [6] Q. Wei, D. Liu, G. Shi, and Y. Liu, "Multibattery optimal coordination control for home energy management systems via distributed iterative adaptive dynamic programming," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 62, no. 7, pp. 4203–4214, 2015.
- [7] G. Liang, E. Rodriguez, G. G. Farivar, E. Nunes, G. Konstantinou, C. D. Townsend, R. Leyva, and J. Pou, "Model predictive control for intersubmodule state-of-charge balancing in cascaded h-bridge converter-based battery energy storage systems," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 71, no. 6, pp. 5777–5786, 2023.
- [8] B. Xu, A. Oudalov, A. Ulbig, G. Andersson, and D. S. Kirschen, "Modeling of lithium-ion battery degradation for cell life assessment," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 1131–1140, 2016.
- [9] X. Wu, X. Hu, Y. Teng, S. Qian, and R. Cheng, "Optimal integration of a hybrid solar-battery power source into smart home nanogrid with plug-in electric vehicle," *Journal of power sources*, vol. 363, pp. 277–283, 2017.
- [10] N. Collath, B. Tepe, S. Englberger, A. Jossen, and H. Hesse, "Aging aware operation of lithium-ion battery energy storage systems: A review," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 55, p. 105634, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2352152X2201622X>
- [11] I. Baccouche, S. Jemmali, B. Manai, N. Omar, and N. Amara, "Improved ocv model of a li-ion nmc battery for online soc estimation using the extended kalman filter," *Energies*, vol. 10, no. 6, p. 764, 2017.
- [12] S. Piller, M. Perrin, and A. Jossen, "Methods for state-of-charge determination and their applications," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 96, no. 1, pp. 113–120, 2001.
- [13] J. Moshövel, K.-P. Kairies, D. Magnor, M. Leuthold, M. Bost, S. Gähns, E. Szczechowicz, M. Cramer, and D. U. Sauer, "Analysis of the maximal possible grid relief from pv-peak-power impacts by using storage systems for increased self-consumption," *Applied Energy*, vol. 137, pp. 567–575, 2015.
- [14] S. Yin, C. Goebel, and H. Hesse, "Boosting the performance of deep reinforcement learning for energy management systems using behavior cloning from linear programming solutions," in *Proceedings of the 16th ACM International Conference on Future Energy Systems (e-Energy '25)*. New York, NY, USA: ACM, Jun. 2025, p. 13. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3679240.3734605>
- [15] A. Le Franc, P. Carpentier, J.-P. Chancelier, and M. De Lara, "Emsx: a numerical benchmark for energy management systems," *Energy Systems*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 817–843, 2023.
- [16] Gurobi Optimization, LLC, "Gurobi Optimizer Reference Manual," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gurobi.com>
- [17] A. Raffin, A. Hill, A. Gleave, A. Kanervisto, M. Ernestus, and N. Dormann, "Stable-baselines3: Reliable reinforcement learning implementations," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 22, no. 268, pp. 1–8, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://jmlr.org/papers/v22/20-1364.html>
- [18] A. Gleave, M. Taufeeque, J. Rocamonde, E. Jenner, S. H. Wang, S. Toyer, M. Ernestus, N. Belrose, S. Emmons, and S. Russell, "imitation: Clean imitation learning implementations," arXiv:2211.11972v1[cs.LG], 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.11972>